

Continuity, Hypothetical Velocity, Photon Ray Theory and Moving Mirror

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In a previous note (1), we used the idea of a hypothetical velocity to solve the problem of incident light (making an angle of AA with the y axis) reflecting from a mirror (lying along the x axis and moving along the y axis with constant speed v) without using special relativity. Here we find the result for $AA=0$. We then try to argue that this follows from a kind of continuity of the wavefunction. (We note that wavefunction continuity is used to solve the one dimensional problem of reflection-refraction at an interface of two indices of refraction).

We then compare the continuity of the wavefunction approach with results of photon ray theory presented in (2).

Hypothetical Velocity Approach

In (1), we developed a hypothetical velocity approach which is equivalent to Fermat's least time method and may be used to derive Snell's law as well as an equation linking the incident and reflected angles of a photon striking a mirror (lying along the x axis) and moving with constant velocity v along the y . The result is:

$$H \cos(90-AA) = (C-v\cos(AA)) \text{ and } H\cos(90-BB) = (c+v\cos(BB)) \quad ((1))$$

Here H is the hypothetical velocity, AA the incident angle relative to the y axis and BB the reflected angle relative to the y axis. V is the velocity of the mirror.

If one arbitrarily sets $AA=BB=0$, then: $H^*0 = c-v$ and $H^*0=c+v$ which is problematic. One may, however, use the following approach. The component of momentum along the x axis, parallel to the mirror surface is conserved as it undergoes no impulse Thus:

$$P(i) \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB) \quad ((2))$$

$P(i)$ is the magnitude of the incident momentum as seen in the lab frame and p_r , the magnitude of the reflected.

$$\cos(90-AA)= \sin(AA) \text{ so } ((1)) \text{ and } ((2)) \text{ yield: } p(i)/p(r) = (c+v) / (c-v) \quad ((3))$$

One may further use: $E_i= p(i) c$ and $E_r = p_r c$ because both the incident and reflected photon move in a vacuum. Thus: $E_i/E_r = (c+v) / (c-v) \quad ((4))$

$((4))$ is exactly the result obtained in (2) using photon ray theory, which is examined later. As noted in (2), photon ray theory does not explicitly use special relativistic Lorentz transforms, but neither does $((2))$.

Continuity of Wavefunction Approach

If one considers a photon moving along the x-axis in a medium with index of refraction $n_1=1$ and hitting an interface at $x=0$ along the y axis where the index of refraction is n_2 for $x>0$, one may use continuity of the wavefunction and first derivative to solve this problem. Considering only the spatial part, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((5a))$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((5b)) \quad \text{and } E=pc = p^2 c/n^2$$

One may then solve for B and C in terms of A.

Given that continuity of the spatial wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is used, we suggest one try to apply it in the case of a photon moving down along the y axis and striking a mirror moving with velocity v along the y axis. In the frame of the moving mirror, this is a usual reflection problem with E_1, p_1 and $E_1, -p_1$ for the incident and reflected beam.

If one writes: $\exp(i py) = \exp(i t p y/t)$, then someone in the lab frame would consider $y/t=c+v$ for the incident photon and $c-v$ for the reflected one, if one were to use the same rules for massive objects. In such a case:

$\exp(it p(i)(c-v))$ should match $\exp(it p_r(c+v))$ where $p(i)$ and p_r are the incident and reflected momenta. Given that time t is the same for both the incident and reflected photon:

$$p(i) / p_r = (c+v) / (c-v) \quad ((6))$$

This matches the result of ((4)). One may note that the hypothetical velocity approach also uses the idea of relative velocities involving light even though a photon is seen as moving with speed c in any constant moving frame.

Photon Ray Theory

We consider photon ray theory presented in (2). This theory considers a changing index of refraction of the form:

$$n(x,y,z,t) = n_1 + \delta n/2 (1 + \tanh(kb y)) \quad ((7))$$

The results of (2) pertaining to a moving mirror, however, do not depend on this form of a changing index of refraction. They are based on (for one dimension i.e. x)

$$E=pc, \quad v_{\text{group}} = dx/dt = dE/dp \quad ((8)) \quad \text{and } E(p,x,t) \text{ or } p(x,t) \text{ and } x(t)$$

(2) presents the key equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } p/i = -d/dx \text{ partial } E + d/dx \text{ partial } p/i \quad d/dt \text{ partial } p/i \quad ((8))$$

This follows from: $W(x,t)=\text{wavefunction}=\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ so: $p/i = d/dx \text{ partial } W$ and $E = -d/dt \text{ partial } W$: so: $d/dt \text{ partial } p/i = -d/dx \text{ partial } E$

$$\text{So } d/dt \text{ full } p/i = -dE/dx \text{ partial} \quad ((9))$$

In other words, the key equations from (2) really follow from the phase of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

Equations ((8)) and ((9)) may then be applied to the moving mirror problem if one uses the math transformation:

$$p'=p \quad \text{and} \quad x'=x-vt \quad \text{where } v \text{ is the velocity of the mirror}$$

One may note that this is again the idea of relative velocity applied to the speed of light c . Here $p/i=k$.

$$\text{Then: } dx'/dt \text{ full} = dE'/dk' \text{ partial} \quad \text{and} \quad dk'/dt \text{ full} = -dE'/dx' \text{ partial}$$

(2) argues that this is consistent with: $E' = E - v p/i$, but $E=c p/i$ ($\hbar=1$) with E' being a constant. Then v is used for the incident ray and $-v$ for the reflected yielding:

$$p(i) / p(r) = (c+v) / (c-v) \quad ((10))$$

We argue that the relationships used for the photon ray theory are essentially linked with $-Et+px$ in the wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + i(p/i) x)$ and so one may go directly to this phase factor as in the continuity argument.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a photon ray theory introduced in (2) which is applied to reflection from a moving mirror (without using Lorentz transformations) seems to be equivalent to treating the absolute value of the phase of $\exp(ip y)$ as being the same for the incident and reflected rays, i.e. using $\exp(i p(i) t y/t)$ and $\exp(i p(r) t y/t)$ with $y/t=c-v$ in the incident case and $c+v$ in the reflected. The phase $-Et+px$ for a particle with rest mass is the classical action. Even though one deals with a photon, it seems that the relevant physics is in this Lorentz invariant phase and so one may find the relationship ((10)) directly from wavefunction phase considerations.

We also show how a hypothetical velocity approach, described in (1) for reflection at an angle with the normal off of a moving mirror, reduces to the case of the incident ray hitting the mirror directly along the y axis, with the mirror along the x -axis. (The mirror moves along y with v).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fermat's Principle and a Hypothetical Velocity Hypotenuse Approach (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
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